

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ANDERSON****FIRST NAME: FRANCES****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium, and the plagiarism rate is: 2%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

Seven key concepts deduced from the EUCLID 2019 ACA-401D coursepack Period one:

1. Originality (EUCLID 2019, 1, 5-7)
2. Literature review (EUCLID 2019, 17-18)
3. Rule of style (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
4. Writing technique (EUCLID 2019, 24; Turabian 2007, 370-373)
5. Language consistency (EUCLID 2019, 27, 56-61)
6. Turabian style vs. Chicago style (EUCLID 2019, 44)
7. American English vs. United Kingdom English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)

AN IN-DEPTH GUIDE FOR INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1. INTRODUCTION

The sixty-one paged EUCLID 2019 ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack for period one revised by Pr. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma holistically address challenges academic writers face. The coursepack has nine chapters and seventy-five subheadings. EUCLID (2019) explains; what a good essay entails, the meaning and types of plagiarism, some rules of thumb for writing academic papers, and how to appropriately structure a literature review. It further enlightens on the importance of style guide, the American and United Kingdom English fundamental disparities and their influences of change, corrections made to sample papers, CMS Crib Sheet, and Latin abbreviations and expressions commonly used in writing.

It is imperative to note that essay writing styles differ, just as each paper has a different topic. To write an essay successfully, the writer has to start early reading, researching, critical thinking, and putting points together; the last-minute rush in writing an academic essay produces undesired results (EUCLID 2019, 1). The paper's first draft will require further reading, organizing ideas, critical thinking, and proper structuring. The

recommended style for structuring an essay is three (3) parts: the introduction, body, and conclusion. The introduction serves as an 'abstract' of an academic paper. It is expected to let readers know what the essay is about but in brief.

Further, the body gives details well pointed out in paragraphs and clarity for readers to flow smoothly. The conclusion summarizes the paper reiterating all the main points highlighted with further research recommendations: the writer should not include any new idea at this point (EUCLID 2019, 2-3). From the facts stated in the coursepack, I deduced that a good essay(irrespective of the topic or language) requires good time for proper research, reading, critical thinking, and early draft, giving the writer ample time to produce a very professional paper.

Period one coursepack had a teaching video by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck on the rule of styles in Microsoft Word, paragraph style, the name convention (canonical). Professor Cleenewerck also taught about the comma's proper use and made all illustrations using the most recent template of the response paper.

2. ORIGINALITY

The clarity in academic writing plays an integral role in the final work of the writer. Therefore, the writer should source appropriate materials and ensure that he or she follows the explicit rules of thumb. In chapter two of EUCLID (2019), I got a lot of insight on the essence of proper citations, which are very helpful in writing, as that will help me (moving forward) to abstain from plagiarism (6). Additionally, I also gathered that quotations should be less and paraphrases appropriately done so that the work will look original, not a duplication of someone else's (EUCLID 2019, 5-7). I find this very insightful. The examples stated in the coursepack, and further reading and research have helped me identify some mistakes I made in previous works. I have attempted to effect those corrections and saved them for future use. When I started my professional career in hospitality, there were very few confident but expensive writers in the part of the globe I was living at the time. I had no choice but to become a writer (though unprofessional). After reading through this coursepack, I have reverted to some of the works I did years back and corrected most of the mistakes. Academic writing is not only technical (which makes it seem difficult); it is also systematic though the process is not a linear one (EUCLID 2019, 1).

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Equally important, a literature review avails the writer the opportunity to go through the works of other writers on the same or similar topic. A literature review is consultations with writers who have done what you are attempting to do. Chapter four of EUCLID (2019) carefully outlines eleven essential inclusions a writer should use when writing a literature review; the points mainly handle proper placements of punctuation marks, showcase the skills required to use conjunctions, and the importance of omitting unnecessary words (17-18). A literature review is 'excellent' if other writers' works are

properly paraphrased and referenced, thereby giving no room for plagiarism. I have always considered this aspect of academic writing the most difficult. The technique to appropriately use a comma to join two independent clauses, followed by a conjunction, was sometimes challenging. I am delighted that Euclid University has exposed me to Grammarly (which I am conveniently using now) and Zotero (though I am still trying to get my way around it). Grammarly is making my writing life easy and exciting.

4. THE "DOS" AND "DONTs"

Another essential point is going by the rules of thumb for academic writing. It is obviously different from other forms of writing. EUCLID (2019) thoroughly explains eight strong points with two subpoints here, which give requisite guidance; in stating the main thesis; staying focused; avoiding the use of generalities; clear writing; supporting assertions; writing interesting papers; taking views discussed seriously, and abstaining from plagiarism (14-16).

Additionally, contrary to what I was taught in high school, up to the postgraduate level, EUCLID (2019, 16) states that the use of the first person singular is appropriate. This clearly shows that the rules change as one climbs the ladder of academia. I may also argue that the doctoral level, as the apex of academic qualifications, requires maturity, which students are expected to have and work on making better.

a) WRITING STYLE

On the other hand, many creative writers elude the use of a style guide as they strongly believe that the beauty of writing is best expressed from within (EUCLID 2019, 24). I think this is an utterly misguided assertion. It makes a lot of sense to consult with others who have gone ahead of you. With creativity, reviewing more than one person's work will make a better read than an individual writer's. It is expedient to note that writing style is not limited to font style and size. It extends to the consistency of paragraph style, which is one of the many benefits I am currently enjoying from Euclid University through the well-structured response paper format. Like every university, Euclid has its rules of style for in-text citations and references (Turabian), recommended English (American) though British English is also acceptable. My exposure to the coursepack also made me realize that I have been very inconsistent in my choice of the English style of writing. EUCLID's guides and templates for the response, quiz, and major papers are well-thought-out. The response paper has given me a lot of hope, and I am confident that by the time I get to the period for quiz and major paper, my writing skills would have significantly improved. Though I started period one less than eleven days ago, I have learned so much from EUCLID, and I am already putting them into practice both professionally and academically.

However, Turabian (2007, 370-373) stated that the book though originally published in 1937 and an upgraded version published in 1996; newer editions were published, and the 2007 copy the most recent. They further asserted that the editors recommended using computers and Times Roman font for research papers, but with few

inconsistencies, the publishers corrected in the seventh edition. I noted that the style of headings, subheadings, and the flashy blue section headings from EUCLID's response paper template is the same as what Turabian (2007, 371) stated. I also noted that the main text in the response template is Times New Roman font size twelve, and the headings on the response paper by order of precedence are fonts twenty, eighteen, sixteen, and fourteen, and the font style is Cambria.

Conversely, EUCLID (2019, 44) informs that the Turabian style is the Chicago style applied to research papers. Though confusing, having read about both types, I can confidently say Chicago and Turabian are very identical, but for the numbering system for notes. Chicago uses a number in parentheses, the year and the information's source, whereas Turabian uses in-text citation in the text of the paper and the footnotes; the year of publication is ensued by its source information.

b) CONSISTENCY IN LANGUAGE

Since World War II, American English has developed progressively in international significance, a development that is opposed to the growth of America's technological, economic, political, and cultural influence globally (EUCLID 2019, 27).

With current dominance on 'world English,' standard American English stands at seventy percent against the standard British English score of seventeen percent of all native English. They both spell most words differently, exempli gratia; center (America) centre (United Kingdom).

As I mentioned earlier, under "WRITING STYLE," looking back, had I known what I know now, my papers would be a lot better than they are. However, I am grateful to Euclid University for this "early" exposure, which has put a complete stop to inconsistency and mixing of American and United Kingdom styles.

Also, EUCLID (2019, 56-61) listed seventy-three common Latin abbreviations used in writing. For instance; c.v. (curriculum vitae), et al. (and other people) i.e. (that is). Again, I have been quite enlightened reading EUCLID's ACA-401D coursepack for period one. I am very sure of an upward trajectory in my academic writing skills

5. CONCLUSION

Period one has been very insightful. I have been able to follow the response paper format set by the university, and I have also acquired additional information on; what a good essay needs, avoiding plagiarism of any sort, reducing quotations, so the work becomes mine, and laid down rules of thumb that must be followed.

Although some writers do not believe in reviewing literature rather solely believe in their "strength from within," it is a fact that papers written by such writers lack professional standards. I have also learned how to use in-text citations and references (the preferred style for Euclid University) Turabian. Period one did not fail to address the

challenges I had with mixing the American English and the United Kingdom English. A practical example of an improvement in my writing skills within eleven days of my enrollment at Euclid University is the increase of my originality and, by extension, vast reduction of my plagiarism rate currently standing at two percent, rated by Grammarly and stated in the template section of this paper.

The conclusion of this paper is that all nine chapters in period one are interconnected. However, I will categorically state that the rule of style, consistency in the use of a particular language type, and adequate literature review are the sine qua nons of a professional essay.

REFERENCES

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